

Additions to the *Etymological Dictionary of Succulent Plant Names,* Part 1: Crassulaceae

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Urs Eggli and Leonard E. Newton's *Etymological Dictionary of Succulent Plant Names* (EDSPN) is a great resource, but – of course – not exhaustive. In this article etymologies are given for several names in the family Crassulaceae not explained in the EDSPN.

CRASSULA GLOBULARIOIDES SUBSP. ILLICHIANA (ENGL.) TOELKEN

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Probably named for Ludwig Illich (ca. 1866–1916), a prominent German settler near Sakare, Western Usambara, German East Africa (present-day Tanzania). According to Adolf Engler's description growing 'auf Felsen von Manca bei Sakare'.

KALANCHOË ELIZAE A.BERGER

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY For Elise Berger née Keller (1869–1944), wife of the botanist Alwin Berger. Having grown up in

London, she probably went by the English form of her given name, Eliza. She died in the Theresienstadt concentration camp.

Elise Berger

Daniel François Malan

Hendrik Frensch
Verwoerd

KALANCHOË GERMANAE RAYM.-HAMET EX RAADTS

EDSPN 'Gen. of Lat. "germanae", sister, brother; application obscure.'

ETYMOLOGY Since Raymond-Hamet named many taxa for women presumably for a woman named Germaine.

KALANCHOË PRAESIDENTIS-MALANII

RAYM.-HAMET (NOM. INVALID.)

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY For Daniel François Malan (1874-1959), prime minister of South Africa (1948-1954). Presumably a plant collected in this country.

***KALANCHOË PRAESIDENTIS-VERWOERDII*¹**

RAYM.-HAMET (NOM. INVAL.) [= *K. BRACHYLOBA*]

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY For Hendrik Frensch Verwoerd (1901-1966), prime minister of South Africa (1958-1966). Presumably a plant collected in this country.

KALANCHOË SOUEGESII

RAYM.-HAMET

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Probably for French botanist Étienne Charles René Souèges (1876-1967).

***PSEUDOSEDUM LIEVENII* (LEDEB.) A.BERGER**

EDSPN 'Unknown.'

ETYMOLOGY Named by Ledebour (1829: 14) 'in piam gratamque memoriam [...] celsissimi Principis Caroli de Lieven, jam supremi per omne Rossiae imperium rerum, quae ad institutionem publicam pertinent, moderatoris'.

General Prince Carl Christoph (Karl Andreyevich) von Lieven (1767-1844) was curator of the University of Dorpat, Governorate of Livonia, Russian Empire (now Tartu, Estonia) during the time Ledebour taught there. In 1828 the not very scientifically minded Lieven wrote to his close advisor Johann Philipp Gustav von Ewers

¹ As *K. praesidentis-verwoerdi*, correctable under ICN Art 60C.3.

(1781-1830), after whom Ledebour had named *Sedum ewersii* Ledeb.: ‘Wenn des guten Ledebour wohlgemeinte Galanterie meinen Namen unter die Pflanzen – doch nicht Giftpflanzen? [sic] – hat bringen wollen, so gefällt mir daran nur dies, dass er auch dort mich in Verbindung mit Ihnen gesetzt hat.’ (Busch 1846: 171)

SEDUM ALMAE FRÖD.

[= *HYLOTELEPHIUM TATARINOWII* (MAXIM.) H. OHBA]

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Probably for Harald August Fröderström’s second wife, Alma Axelina Liedbeck. His grandson Björn Harald Fröderström stated that there is ‘no other possible explanation’ (pers. comm.).

SEDUM BERILLONIANUM RAYM.-HAMET

EDSPN ‘For Dr. Edgar Berilloni (fl. 1913); without further data.’

ETYMOLOGY ‘[Raymond-Hamet] dedicated this species to his colleague Dr. Edgard Bérillon [1859-1948], a French psychiatrist known for his research in hypnosis.’ (Pino et al. 2017)

SEDUM CRASSULARIA (SCHWEINF.) RAYM.-HAMET

EDSPN ‘For the genus *Crassula* and Lat. “-arius”, pertaining to; perhaps for the superficial similarity.’

ETYMOLOGY Named for the now-synonymous genus *Crassularia*, to which it was initially assigned (as *Crassularia sediformis*). This genus was in turn named for the genus *Crassula*.

Carl von Lieven

Edgard Bérillon

Erik Louis Magnus

SEDUM ERICI-MAGNUSII FRÖD.

[SYN. *SEDUM MAGNUSII* RAYM.-HAMET NOM. NUD.]

EDSPN 'For Eric Magnus (fl. 1942), without further data.'

ETYMOLOGY For Swedish industrialist Erik Louis Magnus (1884-1969) (Selling 2019).

SEDUM JINIANUM X.H.GUO

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Perhaps for Xiao Feng Jin or Shui-Hu Jin, Chinese botanists, who, together with Bing Yang Ding, described *Sedum kuntsunianum*.

***SEDUM PURDOMII* W.W.SM.**

EDSPN 'For the botanical collector Purdom (ft. 1916), without further data.'

ETYMOLOGY For British plant explorer William Purdom (1880-1921), who, according to the description, collected the species in Kansu.

***SEDUM STEFCO* STEF.**

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Apparently for a person named Stefan with the Bulgarian nickname Stefčo. The epithet is also rendered in the German spelling *steftscho*, but the international scientific transliteration *stefco* is preferable, even without the diacritic (ICN Art. 60.7). The English spelling would be *stefcho*.

***SEDUM ULRICAE* FRÖD.**

EDSPN n/a

ETYMOLOGY Presumably for Harald August Fröderström's daughter Ulla; Ulrica is the Latin form of this given name. Fröderströms grandson Björn Harald Fröderström stated that there is 'no other possible explanation' (pers. comm.).

LITERATURE

Busch F. (1846). Der Fürst Karl Lieven und die Kaiserliche Universität Dorpat unter seiner Oberleitung. E. J. Karow: Dorpat [Tartu], Leipzig

Eggl U. & Newton L. E. (2004). Etymological Dictionary of Succulent Plant Names. Springer Verlag: Berlin, Heidelberg, New York

Ledebour C. F. von (1828). Icon. Pl.

Pino G. et al. (2017). The Crassulaceae of Cusco Peru: part II: subfamily Sedoideae. Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 89(4): 189-195.

Sánchez de Lorenzo-Cáceres J. M. (2016). Epónimos del género Kalanchoe Adanson (Crassulaceae). *Bouteloua* 23: 43-50.

Selling O. H. (2019). Erik L Magnus. Svenskt biografiskt lexikon, <<https://sok.riksarkivet.se/sbl/artikel/10152>>, accessed 6 February 2019.

IMAGE SOURCES

BERGER: Redies R. (2019). Elise Berger: Gelähmt nach Theresienstadt. Cannstatter Stolperstein-Initiative, <<https://www.stolpersteine-cannstatt.de/biografien/elise-berger-gelaehmt-nach-theresienstadt>>, accessed 6 February 2019.

BÉRILLON: Wikimedia Commons, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Berillon_noframes.jpg>, accessed 6 February 2019.

LIEVEN: Wikimedia Commons, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Lieven_Karl_Andreevich.jpg>, accessed 6 February 2019.

MALAN: Wikimedia Commons, <<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:DFMalanPortret.jpg>>, accessed 6 February 2019.

MAGNUS.: Selling (2019).

VERWOERD: Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Hendrik_Verwoerd_official_photo_1958.jpg>, accessed 6 February 2019.